

Extended Abstract C18**Numerical Investigation of PEEK-Ti Composite Dental Implants Addressing Stress-shielding: Finite Element Analysis**Abdelhak Ouldyyerou¹, Hassan Mehboob^{1*}¹*Department of Engineering Management, College of Engineering, Prince Sultan University, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia*hmeheboob@psu.edu.sa**Abstract**

Stress-shielding remains a major drawback of conventional titanium (Ti) dental implants due to the large mismatch in elastic modulus between Ti and the surrounding bone. Polyetheretherketone (PEEK) has emerged as a promising alternative material owing to its bone-like stiffness, yet its limited strength hinders standalone application. To overcome these limitations, this study numerically investigates composite PEEK–Ti dental implants with tailored reinforcement layouts. A typical implant was modeled using SolidWorks with a volume of 92.77 mm³. Three implant configurations were designed, a single honeycomb Ti bar, three symmetrically arranged honeycomb bars, and seven honeycomb bars filling the PEEK core region. The corresponding Ti reinforcement volumes for the configurations were 5.18 mm³ for the single-bar design, 10.71 mm³ for the three-bar design (3.57 mm³ per bar), and 7.35 mm³ for the seven-bar design (1.05 mm³ per bar). For comparison, fully Ti and fully PEEK implants were also simulated under chewing loading of 200 N using finite element method (FEM). The Mechanostat theory was used to evaluate the biomechanical behavior of the surrounding bone based on the microstrain levels within the bone volume elements. Stresses in the implants and bones were also examined. The results demonstrate that the hybrid PEEK–Ti designs can effectively mitigate stress-shielding by reducing the stiffness mismatch between the implant and bone compared to fully dense Ti. These findings highlight the potential of tailored PEEK–Ti composite implants as a viable solution for optimizing biomechanical performance in dental applications.

Keywords: *Implants; finite element analysis; stress-shielding; PEEK; composite***1. Introduction**

Metal-based implants are widely employed for the repair of large, load-bearing bones because of their high stiffness and excellent mechanical strength [1]. Nevertheless, the mismatch in elastic modulus between metallic implants and native bone can lead to stress-shielding, resulting in bone resorption and implant loosening during long-term clinical use [2]. Researchers have used porous structures with tunable elastic modulus for implant applications [3], especially after advances in additive manufacturing. However, manufacturing-induced defects, including internal flaws such as lack-of-fusion and gas porosity, as well as surface imperfections, are often unavoidable in additively manufactured components and can significantly compromise the structural integrity, ultimately promoting fracture of metal porous-structure. Moreover, such manufacturing defects can introduce geometric irregularities that act as stress concentrators, thereby increasing the likelihood of localized failure and cracks [4]. Polyetheretherketone (PEEK) has attracted increasing attention as a biomaterial for dental implant applications due to its favorable combination of mechanical, biological, and aesthetic properties [5]. As a high-performance thermoplastic polymer, PEEK exhibits an elastic modulus closer to that of bone compared with conventional metallic implant materials, which helps to reduce stress-shielding and improve load transfer to the surrounding bone [6]. With powder bed fusion and vacuum infiltration process, hybrid structures with PEEK penetration and bonding with titanium can be manufactured [7]. This study investigated the biomechanical performance of five configurations of dental implants, including Titanium, PEEK, and three different designs of hybrid composite Ti-PEEK implants.

2. Materials and method

The 3D cross sectional model of the bone was constructed using Solidworks 2020 (Dassault Systèmes, Vélizy-Villacoublay, France). The cancellous bone was surrounded by a 1.5 mm thick layer of cortical bone (bone type II), as shown in Figure 1(a).

2.1. 3D modeling of dental implants

A typical implant was modeled using Solidworks 2020 with a volume of 92.77 mm³. Three implant configurations were designed, a single honeycomb Ti bar (T-P-1), three symmetrically arranged honeycomb bars (T-P-2), and seven honeycomb bars (T-P-3) filling the PEEK core region, as shown in Figure 1(b). The

corresponding Ti reinforcement volumes for the configurations were 5.18 mm³ for the single-bar design, 10.71 mm³ for the three-bar design (3.57 mm³ per bar), and 7.35 mm³ for the seven-bar design (1.05 mm³ per bar). Additionally, two typical implants in this simulation were assigned titanium and PEEK materials. The investigated materials were assumed to be homogeneous, linear elastic, and isotropic. The elastic modulus and Poisson's ratio of all components are summarized in Table 1. While this is a common assumption for FEA, it should be noted that bone exhibits anisotropic and viscoelastic behavior, and PEEK also possesses viscoelastic properties.

Figure 1. 3D modeling. (a); Assembly bone-implant; (b) design configuration of dental implants, and (c) mesh, loading and boundary conditions.

Table 1. Mechanical properties used for FE investigation [7].

	Young's modulus (GPa)	Poisson's ratio
Cortical bone	13.7	0.3
Cancellous bone	1.37	0.3
Titanium	110	0.345
PEEK	3.7	0.3

2.2. Finite element setting

The models were meshed with 10-node quadratic tetrahedron elements (C3D10). The cross-sectional bone was fixed in all directions, as shown in Figure 2. An axial load of 200 N was applied at one reference point coupled with top surface of the implant [3]. All implants were assumed to be 100 % osseointegrated with the bone [8].

3. Results and discussion

Micromotion is the small relative movement that occurs at the interface between the implant and the surrounding bone tissue. Figure 2(a) illustrates the distribution of micromotion within the bone, which varies across different implants. Among the implants, the titanium implant showed the lowest micromotion at 5.96 μm , followed by T-P-2 implant at 8.54 μm , T-P-3 implant at 8.81 μm , T-P-1 implant at 9.39 μm , and the PEEK implant exhibited the highest movement at 11.23 μm , particularly in the cervical region. PEEK exhibited greater micromotion primarily because of its lower elastic modulus compared with the hybrid implants, which have titanium abutments. In contrast, titanium showed the lowest micromotion due to its higher stiffness relative to bone, which imposes greater restrictions on movement at the implant–bone interface.

Figure 2(b) shows the von Mises stress distribution in cancellous bone. It was observed that the PEEK implant exhibited the highest stress concentration in the cervical region of the cancellous bone, while lower stress was seen in the apical region. In contrast, the titanium implant showed more stress concentration at the apical region, with the middle third experiencing the least stress. Among the hybrid implants, a more uniform stress distribution was observed with T-P-2, followed by T-P 3 and T-P-1 implants. The maximum stress in the cancellous bone varied among the different implants. Titanium implant showed the lowest stress at 2.98 MPa, followed by T-P-2 implant at 3.05 MPa, T-P-3 implant at 3.06 MPa, T-P-1 implant at 3.27 MPa,

and PEEK implant exhibited the highest stress at 4.08 MPa. This trend aligns with the observed stress concentration patterns, with PEEK inducing more stress in the cervical region.

Figure 2(c) shows the stress distribution in cortical bone. The stress in the cortical bone varied significantly among the implants. Titanium implant induced the lowest stress at 26.70 MPa, while PEEK implant generated the highest stress at 77.83 MPa. The hybrid implants showed intermediate values, with T-P-3 implant at 63.27 MPa, T-P-2 implant at 65.72 MPa, and T-P-1 implant at 70.76 MPa. These results indicate that stiffer implants like titanium distribute stress more evenly, potentially reducing the risk of marginal bone loss, whereas more flexible materials such as PEEK concentrate stress in the cortical bone. Figure 2(d) illustrates the stresses in the implants. The highest stress was observed in implant T-P-3 (96.84 MPa), followed by T-P-1 (92.10 MPa) and T-P-2 (87.62 MPa). Titanium showed a lower stress value (54.32 MPa), while the lowest stress was recorded in the PEEK implant (44.37 MPa). For the hybrid implants, stresses were concentrated mainly in the titanium bar reinforcement, which carried the majority of the load, whereas the PEEK parts exhibited lower stress distribution.

Figure 2. (a) Micromotion in cancellous bone ($\mu\epsilon$); (b) von Mises stress in cancellous bone (in MPa); (c) von Mises stress in cortical bone and (d) von Mises stress in implants.

Figure 3(a) and Figure 3(b) show the distribution of principal strains in the cancellous bone. Maximum principal strain distribution followed the same trend as the von Mises stress distribution for all implants. Hybrid composite implants exhibited a wider strain distribution compared to homogeneous PEEK and Ti implants. Figure 3(c) illustrates the minimum principal strain in the peri-implant cancellous bone, indicating the proportion of bone elements within the range of 500 $\mu\epsilon$ to 1500 $\mu\epsilon$, which represents the physiologically adapted state (according to mechanostat theory). The titanium implant showed the lowest proportion of bone elements within this range, followed by the PEEK implant. In contrast, all hybrid composite Ti–PEEK implants exhibited a higher proportion of bone elements in the adapted strain range, suggesting reduced bone resorption.

Figure 3. Strains distribution in cancellous bone; (a) Maximum principal strains; (b) minimum principal strains, and (c) minimum principal strains in peri-implant bone (bone elements range in between 500 $\mu\epsilon$ to 1500 $\mu\epsilon$)

4. Conclusions

In this study, homogeneous titanium, PEEK and hybrid composite Ti-PEEK implants (T-P-1, T-P-2, T-P-3) have been investigated using finite element analysis, and the following conclusions can be drawn.

- Titanium implant showed less stress and strain distribution in cancellous bone, which can lead to bone resorption.
- Hybrid T-P-2 implant showed uniformly stress/strain distribution in cancellous bone.
- Hybrid composite implants (T-P-1, T-P-2 and T-P-3) showed more bone elements within adapted state (500 $\mu\epsilon$ to 1500 $\mu\epsilon$).
- PEEK reinforced with Ti can transfer stress to the surrounding bones and therefore can have potential to reduce stress-shielding.

5. Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank Prince Sultan University for their support.

6. References

1. Marin E, Lanzutti A. History of Metallic Orthopedic Materials. *Metals* (Basel). 2025;15: 378. doi:10.3390/met15040378
2. Montet C, Abouelleil H, Labadi C, Gauthier R, Lafon A, Attik N. What enhancement could β -titanium bring to oral implantology? *Dental Materials*. 2025. doi:10.1016/j.dental.2025.11.005
3. Mehboob H, Oulderyou A, Ijaz MF. Biomechanical Investigation of Patient-Specific Porous Dental Implants: A Finite Element Study. *Applied Sciences*. 2023;13: 7097. doi:10.3390/app13127097
4. Syed AK, Ahmad B, Guo H, Machry T, Eatock D, Meyer J, et al. An experimental study of residual stress and direction-dependence of fatigue crack growth behaviour in as-built and stress-relieved selective-laser-melted Ti6Al4V. *Materials Science and Engineering: A*. 2019;755: 246–257. doi:10.1016/j.msea.2019.04.023
5. Qiu P, Bennani V, Cooper PR, Dias G, Ratnayake J. A review of the application of inorganic non-metallic coatings on PEEK dental implants. *Surfaces and Interfaces*. 2025;72: 107027. doi:10.1016/j.surfin.2025.107027
6. Yang Z, Guo W, Yang W, Song J, Hu W, Wang K. Polyetheretherketone biomaterials and their current progress, modification-based biomedical applications and future challenges. *Mater Des*. 2025;252: 113716. doi:10.1016/j.matdes.2025.113716
7. Oulderyou A, Merdji A, Aminallah L, Roy S, Mehboob H, Özcan M. Biomechanical performance of Ti-PEEK dental implants in bone: An in-silico analysis. *J Mech Behav Biomed Mater*. 2022;134: 105422. doi:10.1016/j.jmbbm.2022.105422
8. Mehboob H, Oulderyou A, Al-Tamimi AA, Mehboob A, Barsoum I. Biomechanical analysis of porous and dense dental implant-supported bridges in healthy and osteoporotic bones. *PLoS One*. 2025;20: e0329558. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0329558